

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.8 Dissemination in social media and in the project's home page

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ACRONYMS LIST:

- EFUS: European Forum for Urban Security
- EU: European Union
- FEPSU: Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security
- ISS: International Support Service

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document lists the dissemination in social media and RightsApp home page. In addition, it also contains the dissemination that the collaborators of the project carried out in their main communication channels. This document does not contain statistics nor analysis of the impact of the dissemination activities, this analysis has been performed in RightsApp Deliverable D5.6 – Report on the dissemination activities and their impact into the targeted groups.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	6
2	RightsApp Home Page	8
2.1	News	8
2.2	Online Infoday	9
2.3	Video Tutorials.....	9
2.4	Deliverables	10
2.5	Applications	11
2.6	Identity Set	12
3	Zenodo Community.....	14
4	International Support Service	15
5	Twitter.....	17
6	Collaborators.....	18
6.1	Barcelona City Council	18
6.2	Department of Justice	18
6.3	Mossos d’Esquadra (Home affairs department).....	19

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: News section in the RightsApp Home Page.....	8
Figure 2: Online infoday section in the RightsApp Home Page	9
Figure 3: Tutorials section in the RightsApp Home Page.....	10
Figure 4: Deliverables section in the RightsApp Home Page	11
Figure 5: Mobile applications section in the RightsApp Home Page	12
Figure 6: Identity set section in the RightsApp Home Page.....	12
Figure 7: RightsApp Zenodo Community	14
Figure 8: International Support Service Emergency Protocol web page	16
Figure 9: RightsApp twitter profile in Twitter.....	17
Figure 10: RightsApp project dissemination in the Barcelona City Council Home Page.....	18
Figure 11: RightsApp mobile application has been included as a resource in the “If I am a victim of a crime” section of the Department of Justice of the Public Administration of Catalonia	19
Figure 12: RightsApp project dissemination in the Mossos d’Esquadra News section in its web page	20

1 INTRODUCTION

Throughout the course of the RightsApp project the dissemination strategy has been reshaped to adapt the activities to the new circumstances. Two main events occurred that required a redesign of the dissemination strategy. The first event was that main players in crime victim support became collaborators of the RightsApp project (see RightsApp Deliverable D5.4 – “Mid-project International Workshop”¹ and D5.9 – “Final International Workshop”²):

- Home Affairs and Department of Justice of the Public Administration of Catalonia
- Spanish Red Cross
- Barcelona City Council
- European Forum for Urban Security (EFUS)
- Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security (FEPSU)
- Catalan Society of Victimology

In fact, the Barcelona City Council and the Home Affairs of the Public Administration of Catalonia signed an agreement of collaboration that extends beyond the funding period of the RightsApp project in order to formalize their commitment with the RightsApp initiative. Against this background, the RightsApp research team decided to go beyond the Project’s home page and social media dissemination strategy initially planned, putting efforts on disseminating the project’s achievements through these collaborators that act as multipliers. As a result, the RightsApp project has been disseminated to the general public and stakeholders through: Home Affairs and the Department of Justice of the Public Administration of Catalonia (see Section 6.2 and 6.3) and Barcelona City Council (see Section 6.1). Currently, the RightsApp team is working on disseminating the project to stakeholders through the EFUS and the Catalan Society of Victimology.

The second event that affected the dissemination strategy was the irruption of the COVID-19 pandemic. It has led to a series of restrictions and recommendations that, among others, strongly discourages face-to-face meetings. Thus, several RightsApp activities have been redesigned as online tasks. In particular, dissemination tasks have been highly impacted by this situation. For instance, public events and training sessions were held online in order to minimize risks of contagion for participants and researchers (see RightsApp Deliverable D5.5 – “Four or more training sessions”³).

It is noteworthy to mention that the International Support Service (ISS, formerly International Welcome Point) from the UAB has adopted the RightsApp mobile applications as part of its Emergency Protocol. This institution is part of the UAB and is devoted to support students, researchers and staff that come from abroad to the UAB.

The RightsApp project set up a twitter account to disseminate achievements and share dissemination material. The twitter account has become more active in the last months of the project since the final results have been obtained during this period. Additionally, the RightsApp research team has set up a Zenodo Community for the RightsApp project⁴ where all the public information regarding the project is published.

¹ RightsApp Deliverable D5.4 – Mid-project International Workshop. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/-record/3545857-.X1JT2czZQI>

² RightsApp Deliverable D5.9 – Final International Workshop. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3974190#.X1JT8WczZQI>

³ RightsApp Deliverable D5.5 – Four or more training sessions. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/4014171#.X1JZfWczZQI>

⁴ RightsApp Zenodo Community available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/rightsapp/>

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 lists and shows all the RightsApp Home Page parts that are specifically devoted to dissemination (news, online dissemination materials, deliverables, among others); Section 3 lists the contents and links to the RightsApp Zenodo Community; Section 4 depicts how the International Support Service as adopted RightsApp mobile applications as part of its Emergency Protocol; Section 5 lists the RightsApp Twitter profile; and finally Section 6 shows how the collaborators mentioned above have disseminated the RightsApp project.

2 RIGHTSAPP HOME PAGE

The RightsApp Home Page has become the main point for the dissemination of the project’s achievements and the sharing of public documents. This activity entails different sections that are addressed in this part of the document. The news section is the one that lists and briefs the main project’s achievements. It is a quick and easy way to keep the visitors posted. It includes links to more extensive explanations or download links. The Home Page also encompasses the publication of dissemination documents as the online infoday and tutorial videos for the RightsApp mobile application for Android and iOS versions. Finally, the Home Page also includes a section for the download of the RightsApp mobile applications and its corresponding source code that is available in GitHub⁵.

2.1 News

Figure 1 depicts the news section in the RightsApp Home Page (<http://rightsapp-project.uab.-cat/index.php/news/>). Such news summarises the main achievements of the project, making it easy for the general public and stakeholders to follow the achievements of the project. Each news also contains the links to provide more detailed information for the interested reader. This section also includes an index that allows users to navigate through the news history of the project.

Figure 1: News section in the RightsApp Home Page

⁵ GitHub is a development platform from open source to business that can host code, manage projects and build software alongside 50 million developers. GitHub home page is available at: <https://github.com/>

2.2 Online Infoday

The online infoday is addressed in RightsApp Deliverable D5.7 – “Public events”. The materials are being disseminated in the RightsApp Home Page in Section “RightsApp Infoday presentations”. Here, there are two versions of the Online Infoday presentation: the first one is the Spanish version and the second one is the English version. In addition, the Spanish version has incorporated audio explanations and comments from the project coordinator, Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero. Figure 2 shows the RightsApp Home Page where the Online Infoday materials are available for download (<http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-infoday-presentation/>).

Figure 2: Online infoday section in the RightsApp Home Page

2.3 Video Tutorials

The training sessions held in WP4 were moved to online sessions due to the COVID-19 pandemic. As a support material for this online training sessions, two videos were designed and implemented. They contain a tour for the Android and iOS version of the RightsApp mobile application. Afterwards, an audio explanation of the tour through the mobile applications was added. The resulting videos were published in YouTube in order to disseminate them to the general public, academia and stakeholders. Figure 3

depicts the section in the RightsApp Home Page where the tutorial videos are publicly available (<http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-training-videos/>).

Figure 3: Tutorials section in the RightsApp Home Page

2.4 Deliverables

In addition to the Zenodo Community that is addressed in Section 3, the RightsApp Home Page also makes the project’s deliverables available to the general public, academia and stakeholders. Figure 4 shows the RightsApp Home Page section where the deliverables are publicly available to download (<http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/project-structure/>).

Figure 4: Deliverables section in the RightsApp Home Page

2.5 Applications

This section in the RightsApp Home Page is the main point to download the mobile applications. Both applications are available in their corresponding markets, Google Play Market and Apple Store. However, in this section a link to the page in the market is available to the general public in order to ease the download and installation of the apps. Furthermore, the link to the GitHub page that contains the source code of both versions of the mobile app can be found in this section. Figure 5 shows a screenshot of the section in the project’s home page that is publicly available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-applications/>

Figure 5: Mobile applications section in the RightsApp Home Page

2.6 Identity Set

Figure 6 shows a screenshot of the project’s home page where all materials related to the identity set of the project are publicly available to consult or to download: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/project-identity-set/>

Figure 6: Identity set section in the RightsApp Home Page

The materials provided in this section are:

- Different types of logos in different formats (PNG and JPG)
- Leaflet of the project (PNG and JPG)
- Poster (PNG and JPG)
- Sticker (PNG and JPG)

These materials provide key information for the dissemination of the project: links to the project's home page and downloading options for the mobile applications; information introducing the background and objectives of the project (whenever possible due to space limitations) and QR codes to enable the download and installation of the RightsApp mobile applications.

3 ZENODO COMMUNITY

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program⁶ and operated by CERN⁷. It allows researchers to upload and make data sets, software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts available. For each uploaded item, a persistent digital object identifier is assigned, which makes the stored items easily citable.

The RightsApp project Zenodo community is currently composed by 12 documents. More documents will be added as they become available. Figure 7 lists the available documents and the look and feel of the RightsApp Zenodo community. It offers the possibility to search documents by type, keyword, file format and upload date. In addition, Zenodo provides a persistent platform to make public documents from the project available to the general public, academia and stakeholders.

The number of views and downloads of each deliverable in the Zenodo community are reported in RightsApp Deliverable D5.6 – “Report on the dissemination into the targeted groups”. At the time of writing, the uploaded documents reach 560 views and 297 downloads.

Figure 7: RightsApp Zenodo Community

⁶ OpenAIRE mission is to provide unlimited, barrier free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe.

OpenAIRE Home Page is available at: <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁷ CERN Home Page is available at: <https://home.cern/>

4 INTERNATIONAL SUPPORT SERVICE

The International Support Service's (ISS, formerly International Welcome Point) main target is to provide information for students, teachers, and administrative and service staff from other countries. At the ISS, newcomers: (i) will find all the information they need upon arrival; (ii) will be able to find answers to any questions about academic life; (iii) get the UAB student card; (iv) learn about the activities that take place on campus; (v) find out about available scholarships; (vi) receive personalized attention to find accommodation (vii) inquire about the university's services and, (viii) see which language courses they can enrol in. At the ISS, people from abroad will also find information on how to get to the UAB, information about accommodation, the cost of living, services on campus, as well as important phone numbers.

Additionally, the ISS offers in its home page an Emergency protocol to support people from abroad that face a problem once they are living in Barcelona. Figure 8 is a screenshot that shows this protocol and the available institutions that could provide support if needed. After the publication of the RightsApp mobile application, it becomes part of this protocol. The Emergency protocol is publicly available at: <https://www.uab.cat/web/mobility-international-exchange/international-support-service/travel-abroad-1345819434765.html>

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Study | Research | Life on campus | About the UAB

INTERNATIONAL SUPPORT SERVICE

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona | Mobility & International Exchange | International Support Service | Travel abroad

International Support Service

- Home
- News

International Students

- Non-EU
- EU and Schengen
- Living in Barcelona

International Teachers and Researchers

- Non-EU
- EU and Schengen
- Living in Barcelona

Invited Personnel

- Visitors Registration

Emergency Protocol

- Travel abroad
- Travel to Barcelona

Travel abroad

MAEC RECOMMENDATIONS

Before travelling abroad is important to keep oneself well-informed in order to avoid problems or emergency situations. [MAE's website](#) supplies useful information for every other trip abroad. [In this website](#) you will find a list of every Spanish embassy in the world. It is recommended to look into every other information regarding the country you are planning to travel to since in there you will find up-to-date tips regarding the requisites of how would it be to enter into the country, the documentation and visas needed to do it so as well as the security and sanitary levels or important phone numbers that can come in handy. In collective emergency situations such as a natural catastrophe it is very important to check the security sections as well as the notice section each embassy has on their website with updated news regarding the country's situation.

CONSULAR ASSISTANCE

It is also very important to know what kind of help consulates and embassies are able to provide. Especially if you find yourself in a difficult personal situation regarding your well-being. You can check the Consular Attendance information of MAE [here](#). [Emergency numbers](#)

CONSULAR REGISTRATION

The registration of the consular enrollment is a public register that is done within the Spanish Consular Offices that can be found abroad. The enrollment is done following the Spanish citizens that live within the proper consular limits, being regular citizens or just in passing. These consular registrations allows you to receive proper diplomatic protections in case of emergency, being that a natural catastrophe, a sanitary emergency, military conflict, a mere accident or a personal situation that may ask for a consular protection. In the case of an abroad mobility stay it is recommended to fill up the form as being "nonresident" so, if an emergency might happen, they can be contacted by the correspondent consular office.

- For trips less of 3 months long: [Traveler's Register](#)
- For trips of more than 3 months long: [Consular Inscription](#)

ONLINE TEACHING

It must be taken into account that according to the sanitary authorities and following the extraordinary measures that must have been taken in order to prevent one being infected by Covid-19, there can be some cases in where online teaching must be done rather than in-class learning, be that at the beginning of your stay or halfway during it.

VACCINES

In order to prevent the contraction of any kind of illness the World Health Organization recommends—or compels, depending on the case— to get your vaccines done before traveling internationally. Catalonian vaccination centers supply an individualized care regarding the shots one must take depending on the country, time of the year, type and duration of the trip. You can find more information in the following link: [International Vaccination_Gencat](#)

HEALTH INSURANCE

Among the EU

For stays within the European Union its highly recommended to get the [European Healthcard card](#), which gives you the rights to receive the sanitary perks that might be needed during your temporary stay within the Schengen borders according to the rules and legislations of the host country. In some cases, a fixed amount of money or percentage will be needed to be paid in order to get the full coverage in the same conditions that the citizens of the country itself so it is also recommended to have a [healthcare insurance](#) that includes coverage in case of Covid-19. [UAB's complementary insurance](#) covers such case but it merely gives you a threshold of 6.000 euros, reason as of why an additional insurance of a 300.000 minimum coverage is also recommended. [Crimibus](#) offers such kind of insurance but any other that follows these rules would also be acceptable.

Outside the EU

For mobility programs that are outside the European union borders is highly advisable to have a health insurance that covers every possible Covid-19 treatment expenses. [UAB's complementary insurance](#) covers such case but it merely gives you a threshold of 6.000 euros, reason as of why an additional insurance of a 300.000 minimum coverage is also recommended. [Crimibus](#) offers such kind of insurance but any other that follows these rules would also be acceptable.

WEATHER FORECAST

Depending on where you plan to travel you might find very diverse climatology. It is recommended to be up-to-date of every other possible condition you might encounter. The following links can aid on that regard:

- [Meteoalarm](#)
- [Organización Meteorológica Mundial](#)

RightsApp

UE citizens- under a certain set of rules- have the right to move freely within the UE borders. European rules, abided to the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice, are to secure the right of the citizens so they are protected when they are in a Member State that is not their own. The RightsApp is a phone app that can be found in [four different languages](#) (English, Spanish, Italian and Portuguese) and covers all three sceneries that can be followed in case you find yourself in need of help. The first case would be to [call 112](#). By only pressing a button you will be able to make the call. The second case focuses in the [information available to the rights covered by those within the UE borders](#). After a quick survey the rights that can help to the app user are made available. The third and last use of the app covers the [entities and help centers to those who have suffered any kind of crime in Catalonia](#).

- [Link Android](#)
- [Link IOS](#)

International Support Service

ISS team

ISS team

ARI Staff

ARI Staff

International Support Service (ISS)

Edifici Biblioteca de Comunicació i Hemeroteca
General
Plaça Cívica
Campus de Bellaterra

Tel: +34 88 581 22 10
international.support@uab.cat

Schedule:
Monday to Friday, from 9:30 a.m. to 3:00 p.m.
Thursday from 9:30 a.m. to 4:30 p.m.

Figure 8: International Support Service Emergency Protocol web page

5 TWITTER

The dissemination strategy considered from the beginning of the project entails the creation and update of a twitter account for the project. The main objective of this account is to share the achievements and project outcomes with the general public, academia and stakeholders. Every day the twitter account is more and more active since dissemination materials, achievements and project outcomes are now available. However, the analysis of statistics and impact on the targeted groups is implemented in RightsApp Deliverable D5.6 – Report on the dissemination activities and their impact into the targeted groups.

Figure 9 depicts a screenshot of the Twitter profile for the RightsApp project which contains the project’s logo and the acknowledgement of funding by the European Union’s Justice Programme (2014-2020).

Figure 9: RightsApp twitter profile in Twitter

6 COLLABORATORS

At the moment of writing this document, three collaborating institutions have disseminated the RightsApp project through the common dissemination channels in their web pages. The Barcelona City Council and Mossos d’Esquadra (as part of the Catalan Home Affairs Department) published an announcement in their News section. Both texts contain a brief description of the project and QR codes and links to download and install the mobile app. In addition, the Department of Justice of the Public Administration of Catalonia has included the RightsApp mobile application as a resource available to citizens in the section “If you have been a victim of a crime” in its web page. The following section lists the link to the information published and a screenshot of the web page.

6.1 Barcelona City Council

Figure 10 depicts a screenshot of the article published in the News section of the Barcelona City Council web page. The information is available at: <https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/seguretatiprevencio/ca/noticia/en-funcionament-laplicacize-rightsapp>

Figure 10: RightsApp project dissemination in the Barcelona City Council Home Page

6.2 Department of Justice

Figure 11 shows the section “I am a victim of a crime” in the Department of Justice web page. In this section the RightsApp mobile application is introduced as an additional resource available for citizens.

This section is available at: https://sejudicial.gencat.cat/ca/que_cal_fer/Soc-victima-de.../victima-delicte/index.html

Figure 11: RightsApp mobile application has been included as a resource in the “If I am a victim of a crime” section of the Department of Justice of the Public Administration of Catalonia

6.3 Mossos d’Esquadra (Home affairs department)

Figure 12 depicts a screenshot of the news published in the News section of the Mossos d’Esquadra web page as part of the Catalan Home Affairs Department. In this text, the background and objectives of the project are explained. In addition, the QR codes to the RightsApp Home Page and the links to download and install the mobile applications are included. The news is available at: https://mossos.gencat.cat/ca/detalls/Noticia/noticia_projecte_Rightsapp

Figure 12: RightsApp project dissemination in the Mossos d'Esquadra News section in its web page